

Perceived Level of Motivation Among Working College Students in the New Normal Education

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Abstract:

Working to meet needs is essential to all humankind and enables the person to engage in all activities in life in order to improve themselves by motivating the inner self to work hard. Students are driven by motivation, which propels them to significant academic performance. Motivation plays a crucial role in the academic performance of working students. The study explored the relationship between the perceived level of motivation and academic performance of working college students in a local city college. Using adopted questionnaires based on established research from P. A. Creed, J. French, and M. Hood (2015), the study measures students' motivation while utilizing their grades to assess academic performance. The relationship between work benefits and demands and engagement and well-being while the grades/remarks of the respondents were utilized as their academic performance. The sample consisted of 136 respondents from various departments. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and Likert scale were employed to interpret the data, while Pearson Correlation tested the association between the variables. The results indicated a slightly negative correlation between motivation and academic performance, suggesting that as motivation decreases, academic performance may also decline. The findings highlight the significant impact of motivation on academic outcomes among working students. It is recommended that the college adopt an action plan within student affairs to enhance motivation and support academic achievement. This study contributes to the literature by addressing the unique challenges faced by working students in the new normal education setup and offers practical solutions to improve their academic success.

Keywords: Level of Motivation, Academic Performance, Working College Students and New Normal Education

Introduction:

A perceived level of motivation for all students, especially working students, can improved their performance in all walks of life. When working students believed in their potential and are motivated to succeed, they are more likely to approach challenges with a can-do attitude, embrace learning opportunities, and persist in the face of difficulties. According to

Abenoja et al., (2019) understanding why students choose to work and study simultaneously and identifying groups facing greater difficulties is crucial. One of the primary motivations for working students is the pursuit of financial independence. Many students shoulder the responsibility of paying for their education, living expenses, and other financial obligations. By working alongside their studies, they gain a sense of empowerment and self-sufficiency, which can fuel their motivation. The desire to create a better future for themselves and alleviate financial burdens acts as a driving force, propelling them to persevere despite the challenges they face. Financial constraints often drive students from less privileged backgrounds to work more hours, while those from more privileged backgrounds work fewer hours for financial independence (Sanchez Gelabert & Elias, 2017). However, this phenomenon's impact on academic performance remains significant. They hypothesize that the average grade of working students will significantly influence their academic performance, as motivated students have a stronger drive to excel and secure a better future (Kori et al., 2016). When working students have to allocate a significant amount of time and energy to their jobs, they may have less time available for attending classes, participating in extracurricular activities, or seeking additional academic support. This reduced focus on academics can result in lower grades and a decreased ability to fully engage in their studies. The researcher observed that some working students face various problems, like expenses such as housing, transportation, allowance, electricity, food, and leisure activities. Balancing work and studies can be challenging, with students taking on significant responsibilities. The stress of managing multiple responsibilities, meeting deadlines, and dealing with financial pressures can negatively impact their focus, motivation, and overall mental health. This can further hinder their ability to perform well in class, which is why some working students experienced difficulties with class deliverables and proper time management. Proper time management is crucial for working students. They must carefully balance their work hours, class schedules, study time, and personal commitments. The demands of their jobs can often disrupt their study routines and require them to make adjustments to their schedules. Without effective time management skills, working students may struggle to find the right balance, resulting in feelings of overwhelm and an increased risk of burnout. Motivation plays a crucial role in the academic performance of working students. By fostering a sense of motivation, educators can have inspired and empower students to excel in both their jobs and studies. Financial independence serves as a significant driving force for many working students, as they strive to create a better future for themselves and overcome financial constraints. This study aimed to investigate the relationship between the perceived level of motivation and academic performance of working college students enrolled in Mandaue City College, second semester.

Review of Related Literature:

(Abenoja R. et al. 2019) As stated in their study that being a working a student is difficult and requires a lot of responsibilities. They feel more in control of their decisions and behaviors as a result. While working, students also pick up a lot of experiences and ideas that might benefit their personal lives and their ability to solve problems. In the case of students studying for a degree who have chosen to work and study with difficulties in both working and learning, as stated by Sara R. et al 2022. They are often late to work and school and find it too difficult to complete their assignments because they are exhausted from work (2020 Tulin et al). As stated in Lesskowsky F. and Unger M. 2022, the rate of retention for students is influenced by student employment. Studies show that working during school can be advantageous for students such as their employability, but excessive work may negatively influence academic progress. (Acaso M. et al. 2019) As reported in their research student are taking up part time work to earn extra income. It significantly affects how well students succeed academically. This circumstance may have both be. Kkzkan 2015, defining motivation as the sum total of efforts which have been made to mobilize individuals towards one or several specific objectives, while ensuring that such a movement is maintained. Conforming to Waterman (2013) it's a workforce describing the inner deputies establishing the moves that should exist achieved to complete a want and the extrinsic factors that nourish this behavior. When a factor that influences an individual's behavior is based on his own internal world, independent from the drives outside of him, it constitutes intrinsic motivation Ural, 2011. Actions which are performed through intrinsic motivation and which originate from these sources are inherently rewarding for the individual, thus no additional motive or punishment is needed (Şen 2012). In this case, the individual is expected to display behaviors such as volunteerism, willingness and making a choice (Deci and Ryan 2016). Thus, intrinsic results from these activities are usually personal experiences with meaning for each individual according to Erdoan 2013). If the motivation of a person's behavior is independent of his or her environment, in other words, if it's in his or her environment, then that's extrinsic motivation. The behaviors which originate from external sources, such as rewards, punishment, and social support, are behaviors which are linked with the result of the individual's action (Erdoğan 2013). In this regard, the individual is not motivated by any interest in the action itself but rather he is motivated by the benefits that this action brings (Şen 2016). The importance of motivation in influencing human behaviour and performance, as defined by Yuan et al. 2014, Turan 2015, is considered to be a key factor. Especially informational experimenters and interpreters express that provocation is one of the most important factors in student accomplishment and in insuring nonstop achievement (Pintrich and Schunk 2012). For instance, Lin 2012 describes provocation as a natural desire that has been essential in individualities or reflected in them while they acquire new knowledge and experience. There are, still, in the literature other descriptions of boost; the ultimate word was deduced from the word "movere" that means moving in Latin (Seiler et al. 2012). In this account, corresponding to Ertem (2016), motivation is an internal state showing up beings, conduct and directing them to these actions; still, according to Baumeister and Vohs (2017), this is the state in which individuals, acting on their own volition, show different views to achieve a specific objective. Tohidi and Jabbari (2011) suggest that motivation is the drive that propels people to go through significant performance barriers. Williams and Williams (2011) labeled this as exerting effort in order to achieve results. From the

aforementioned, it can be inferred that motivation is the initiator, driving force, and persistence of human behavior change. Student motivation, however, may be thought of as the force that propels, inspires, shapes, and stimulates students' academic success. According to research on the significance of students' motivation for attainment and performance, a highly motivated person is more likely to be dedicated to achieving the organizational goals and objectives (Fakunle, 2016). This leads us to the conclusion that motivated employees are assets to the development of the organization, notwithstanding all obstacles. Likewise, students that are very motivated frequently achieve academically (Ohadugha et al., 2020). According to Adamma et al (2018).s research, motivation boosts students' academic performance regardless of gender. Working while studying exposes students to real-world experiences and enhances their understanding of different professional fields, providing a practical education (Richardson, Evans, & Gbadamosi, n.d.). Students who work up to 20 hours per week have a higher likelihood of completing college, and on-campus employment often involves academic tasks that complement their studies (BYU Employment Services, 2010). Palmer's (2011) assertion that the primary driver of high-quality education is student motivation. From this concept, a school's output—student performance—is equivalent to high-quality instruction. Being successful in school is the main goal of the modified teaching-learning during the pandemic, therefore motivating working students to succeed throughout the introduction of the "new normal" (online learning) is a major challenge. To summarized, there are two important factors in the concept of motivation.

Research Method:

This study used quantitative approach and employed the descriptive-correlational method to determine the perceived level of motivation among working college students in the new normal education in Mandaue City College. Descriptive design attempts to examined situations in order to established what the norm is, while correlational attempts to examine a relationship between concepts (Walliman, 2011). Mandaue City College (MCC) served as the primary research environment for the study. Located at Don Andres Soriano Avenue, Barangay Centro, Mandaue City. The selection of respondents from the pool of officially enrolled working college students ensured that the study captured the perspectives and experiences of individuals who were actively involved in balancing work and academics within the MCC community. This approach allowed for a more targeted and meaningful analysis of the research objectives. Incidental Sampling is used which refers to a non-probability sampling technique in the study, where the selection of participants or subjects is based on their availability or convenience rather than a predetermined sampling method. In incidental sampling, individuals are included in the study based on their accessibility and proximity to the researcher or research setting. Lastly, the study aimed to account for these variations in order to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon of the study.

Results and Discussion:

The results of the study indicated that the majority of the respondents achieved a General Weighted Average (GWA) of 1.9, which accounted for 22.79 percent of the total respondents, followed by a GWA of 2.0, accounting for 18.38 percent. This suggested that a considerable proportion of the working college students performed well academically during the specified semester. However, there were only a few respondents who obtained GWAs of 1.3 and 2.8, indicating that they had relatively lower academic performance. The total number of actual research respondents was one hundred thirty-six (136), representing 100 percent of the surveyed population.

Table 1.
Financial Aspects of the Working Students

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
How motivated are you to work while studying to meet your financial needs?	3.80	Motivated
How much does the need to support yourself financially influence your decision to work while studying?	3.80	Motivated
How motivated are you by the desire to earn money while studying?	3.77	Motivated
How motivated are you to work while studying to cover the costs of educational and living expenses?	3.77	Motivated
How much does the financial independence provided by having a job while studying motivate you?	3.77	Motivated
How motivated are you to recommend working while studying to other students facing financial challenges?	3.73	Motivated
Weighted Mean	3.77	Motivated

Legend:4: 20 – 5:00 -Very Motivated (VM); 3:40 – 4:19 – Motivated (M); 2:00 – 3: 39 – Undecided (U); 1: 80 – 2: 59 – Less motivated (LM);

1:00 – 1: 79 – Not Motivated (NM)

Table 1 showed that the provided data for the Financial Aspect of motivation, the respondents expressed a generally positive level of motivation in relation to working while studying to meet their financial needs, with the weighted mean of 3.77. The respondents reported a mean score of 3.80, indicating that they felt motivated to work while studying in order to meet their financial needs. This suggests that financial considerations played a significant role in their decision to work alongside their studies. This study conducted by the Institute for Employment Studies (IES) and their research partners at NatCen (2014). The motivations for students to work while studying are primarily driven by financial need, flexibility, and convenience. Students may take on paid work to cover essential expenses or to address financial emergencies. Similarly, Creed, French, and Hood (2015) found that financial considerations significantly influence the engagement and well-being of students who work while studying. Their research indicated that students who manage to secure employment that is flexible and accommodating of their academic schedule tend to report higher levels of motivation and satisfaction. The weighted mean score of 3.77 in this study reflects a generally positive level of motivation among respondents, emphasizing that financial needs are a critical factor in their decision to work. This suggests that addressing the financial challenges faced by students through supportive policies and flexible work arrangements could enhance their motivation and academic performance.

Table 2
Class Deliverables of the Working Students

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
How motivated are you to actively participate in online class discussions and activities?	3.84	Motivated
How motivated are you to attend virtual classes and lectures regularly?	3.78	Motivated
How motivated are you to complete online assignments and projects on time?	3.77	Motivated
How motivated are you to adapt to the new learning technologies and tools used in online education?	3.76	Motivated
How motivated are you to seek help and support from your professors or instructors in the online learning environment?	3.75	Motivated
How motivated are you to collaborate with classmates through online platforms for group projects or assignments?	3.74	Motivated
Weighted Mean	3.74	Motivated

Legend: 4: 20 – 5:00 -Very Motivated (VM); 3:40 – 4:19 – Motivated (M); 2:00 – 3: 39 – Undecided (U); 1: 80 – 2: 59 – Less motivated (LM); 1:00 – 1: 79 – Not Motivated (NM)

The table 2 showed that the provided data for the Class Deliverables of motivation, the respondents expressed a generally positive level of motivation in relation to various aspects of their academic performance and engagement in online education, with the weighted mean of 3.74. Palmer's (2011) assertion that the primary driver of high-quality education is student motivation. From this concept, a school's output—student performance—is equivalent to high-quality instruction. Being successful in school is the main goal of the modified teaching-learning during the pandemic, therefore motivating working students to succeed throughout the introduction of the "new normal" (online learning) is a major challenge. This aligns with findings from various studies that highlight the critical role of motivation in ensuring student success in an online learning environment. For instance, a study by Wang, Shannon, and Ross (2013) found that students' self-regulation and intrinsic motivation are key predictors of their engagement and performance in online courses. Furthermore, the transition to the "new normal" of education has necessitated modifications in teaching and learning strategies to support student motivation. This includes the implementation of interactive and flexible learning approaches that cater to the needs of working students.

Table 3.
Time Management of the Working Students

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
How motivated are you for considering your time management practices and identifying areas for improvement?	3.16	Undecided
How motivated are you to prioritize tasks and allocate time accordingly to meet deadlines?	3.14	Undecided
How motivated are you to minimize distractions and stay focused on your tasks during designated study/work periods?	3.14	Undecided
How motivated are you to effectively balance your work and study commitments to avoid burnout?	3.14	Undecided
How motivated are you to regularly review and adjust your schedule to accommodate changes in your work and study requirements?	3.14	Undecided
How motivated are you to create and follow a schedule to manage your work and study commitments effectively?	3.13	Undecided
How motivated are you to set realistic goals and milestones for your academic and work-related responsibilities?	3.13	Undecided
Weighted Mean	3.14	Undecided

Legend: 4: 20 – 5:00 – Very Motivated (VM); 3:40 – 4:19 – Motivated (M); 2:00 – 3: 39 –Undecided (U); 1: 80 – 2: 59 – Less motivated (LM); 1:00 – 1: 79 – Not Motivated (NM)

The table 3 showed that the provided data for the Time Management aspect of motivation, the respondents expressed a generally undecided or neutral level of motivation in relation to various aspects of effectively managing their time while working and studying. The Association of Community College Trustees (Beer & Bray, 2019) acknowledges that many students balance work and school. Students are expected to efficiently manage their time to handle their demanding schedules. A study by Broadbent and Poon (2015) underscores the importance of time management in academic success, particularly in online learning environments. Their research found that students who employ effective time management strategies, such as setting clear goals and prioritizing tasks, tend to achieve higher academic performance. These strategies include creating structured schedules that allocate adequate time for both academic and work-related activities. Effective time management also leads to improved self-discipline, which is crucial for maintaining a balance between work and academic commitments.

Table 4.
Perceived Level of Motivation (Summary)

INDICATORS	Mean	Categorical Responses
Financial Aspect	3.77	Motivated
Classroom Deliverables	3.74	Motivated
Weighted Mean	3.55	Motivated
Time Management	3.14	Undecided
Standard Deviation	0.257	

The table 4 showed that the respondents' perceived level of motivation during their second semester in the Academic Year 2021-2022 is generally positive. The general weighted mean of the perception level connotes on 3.55 or equivalent to "Motivated" while the standard deviation is 0.257 which is remarkably possible and clearly navigated based on the given variables of the study. According to Adamma et al (2018).s research, motivation boosts students' academic performance regardless of gender. The positive level of motivation observed in the study is crucial, especially in the context of the ongoing challenges posed by the pandemic. Research by Dumford and Miller (2018) indicates that students' motivation levels can be significantly impacted by their learning environment. In the shift to online learning, maintaining high levels of motivation is essential for student success. Institutions can support this by providing engaging and interactive online learning experiences, as well as resources to help students manage their time and stay motivated.

Table 5.
 Academic Performance

General Weighted Average (GWA)	Frequency	Percentage
1.9	31	22.79
2.0	25	18.38
1.7	22	16.18
1.8	19	13.97
1.6	15	11.03
1.5	8	5.88
2.1	7	5.15
1.4	5	3.68
2.2	2	1.47
1.3	1	0.74
2.8	1	0.74
1.85	136	100.00

The table 5 showed that the clustered General Weighted Average of the total respondents. It is noted that most of the respondents has the General Weighted Average of 1.9 or equivalent to 22.79 percent and 2.0 or equivalent to 18.38 while only a few respondents got the General Weighted Average of 1.3 and 2.8 or equivalent to 0.74. The majority of the respondents performed well academically, with a significant portion achieving GWAs within the range of 1.9 to 2.0. This suggests that a significant proportion of the working college students achieved consistently good grades throughout the semester. Working while studying exposes students to real-world experiences and enhances their understanding of different professional fields, providing a practical education (Richardson, Evans, & Gbadamosi, n.d.). Students who work up to 20 hours per week have a higher likelihood of completing college, and on-campus employment often involves academic tasks that complement their studies (BYU Employment Services, 2010). Moreover, the positive correlation between academic performance and work-study experiences is supported by literature exploring the benefits of experiential learning. By engaging in work-related activities, students develop valuable skills such as time management, problem-solving, and communication, which are essential for success in both academic and professional contexts (Kolb, 2014).

Additionally, the concept of "learning by doing" is central to the experiential learning theory proposed by Kolb (2014). According to this theory, individuals learn best through hands-on experiences and reflection on those experiences. Working while studying provides students with opportunities to apply theoretical concepts in real-world settings, reinforcing their understanding and retention of course material.

Table 6.

Perceived Motivation Level and Academic Performance

Correlations			
		Motivation Level	Academic Performance
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.402	
	Sig. (2- tailed)		.402
	N	136	136
	N	136	136
Motivation Level	Pearson Correlation	1	-.072
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	-.072	1

The table 6 showed that the test of the relationship between perceived motivation level and academic performance among the respondents. The significance value of 0.402 indicates that the null hypothesis of the study is rejected. This suggests that there is a relationship between the variables, albeit a *slightly negative correlation* of -0.072. The findings reveal that “*perceived motivation level*” and “*academic performance*” are *highly significant* to each other, as indicated by a significance level of 0.05. Fakunle (2016), the significance of students' motivation for attainment and performance, a highly motivated person is more likely to be dedicated to achieving the organizational goals and objectives. Motivated employees are assets to the development of the organization, notwithstanding all obstacles. Likewise, students that are very motivated frequently achieve academically (Ohadugha et al., 2020)

Conclusion:

This study concluded that there is a high significant relationship between the perceived level of motivation and the academic performance of working college students in the new normal education environment, which means that their level of motivations and confidence in adopting the blended online learning are strong and safe. Teachers must motivate their students along the way in the online course. By this, the Self-determination Theory (SDT) by Deci & Ryan (2016) defined as people tend to become happier when pursuing things that are intrinsically motivated and are aligned with their own goals – it not only makes them feel more responsible about the outcomes, it also helps them to really focus their time on what they want to be doing. In addition, the social cognitive theory supported the findings of this study that learners, who are highly self-regulated, exhibit effective positive motivation and self-efficacy concerning their learning processes through selecting learning content, identifying learning goals, and organizing and controlling their learning.

Recommendation:

Based on the following the findings of the study, the researcher recommends to explore additional factors that may influence the motivation and academic performance of working college students in the new normal education context. This can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics and challenges faced by this student population and inform the development of tailored interventions and support systems. The proposed Motivation Enhancement Program, is highly recommended for implementation. This program aims to enhance and sustain the motivation levels of working college students in the new normal education environment. By implementing this program, educators can create a supportive and engaging atmosphere that fosters students' intrinsic motivation and facilitates their academic success. Teachers and educators should focus on fostering intrinsic motivation among working college students. By creating engaging and meaningful learning experiences, incorporating students' interests and goals, and providing opportunities for autonomy, educators can enhance students' motivation and overall engagement in the online learning process. Educators should provide guidance and support in helping students develop effective self-regulation strategies, such as goal-setting, time management, and self-monitoring. These skills can enable students to take control of their learning process and enhance their academic performance. Administrators should provide necessary resources and support to ensure an effective and conducive learning environment. Further research is recommended to explore additional factors that may influence the motivation and academic performance of working college students in the new normal education context. This can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics and challenges faced by this student population and inform the development of tailored interventions and support systems.

References:

- Amrai K., Motlagh S. E., Zalani H. A. and Parhon H. 2011 The relationship between academic motivation and academic achievement students *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.03.111>
- Bandura, A., & Schunk, D. H. (2014). Cultivating competence, self-efficacy, and intrinsic interest through proximal self-motivation. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 41(3), 586-598. DOI:[10.1037/0022-3514.41.3.586](https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.41.3.586)
- Calderwood, C., Ackerman, P. L., & Conklin, E. M. (2014). What else do college students "do" while studying? An investigation of multitasking. *Computers & Education*, 75, 19-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.02.004>
- Carlson, D. S., Bozeman, D. P., Kacmar, M. K., Wright, P. M., & McMahan, G. C. (2018, Fall). Training motivation in organizations: An analysis of individual-level antecedents. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 12, 271-287. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734371X19876676>
- Credé, M., Roch, S. G., & Kieszczyńska, U. M. (2010). Class attendance in college: A meta-analytic review of the relationship of class attendance with grades and student characteristics. *Review of Educational Research*, 80(2), 272-295. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654310362998>
- Creed P. A., French J. and Hood M. 2015 Working while studying at university: The relationship between work benefits and demands and engagement and well-being *J. Vocat. Behave.* DOI:[10.1016/j.jvb.2014.11.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2014.11.002)
- Dennis, J. M., Phinney, J. S., & Chuateco, L. I. (2012). The role of motivation, parental support, and peer support in the academic success of ethnic minority first-generation college students. *Journal of college student development*, 46(3), 223-236. DOI:[10.1353/csd.2005.0023](https://doi.org/10.1353/csd.2005.0023)
- Devlin, M., James, R., & Grigg, G. (2018). Studying and working: A national study of student finances and student engagement. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 14, 111-122. doi:[10.1080/1358388080205304](https://doi.org/10.1080/1358388080205304)
- Eom, S. B., Wen, H. J., & Ashill, N. (2014). The determinants of students' perceived learning outcomes and satisfaction in university online education: An empirical investigation. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education*, 4(2), 215-235. DOI:[10.1111/j.1540-4609.2006.00114.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4609.2006.00114.x)
- Hollembeak, J., & Amorose, A. J. (2013). Perceived coaching behaviors and college athletes' intrinsic motivation: A test of self-determination theory. *Journal of applied sport psychology*, 17(1), 20-36. DOI:[10.1080/10413200590907540](https://doi.org/10.1080/10413200590907540)
- Jordan, A. E. (2012). College student cheating: The role of motivation, perceived norms, attitudes, and knowledge of institutional policy. *Ethics & Behavior*, 11(3), 233-247. DOI:[10.1207/S15327019EB1103_3](https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327019EB1103_3)
- Kusurkar, R. A., ten Cate, T. J., Vos, C. M. P., Westers, P., & Croiset, G. (2013). How motivation affects academic performance: A structural equation modelling analysis. *Advances in Health Sciences Education*, 18(1), 57-69. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-012-9354-3>
- Martin, K., Galentino, R., & Townsend, L. (2014). Community college student success: The role of motivation and self-empowerment. *Community College Review*, 42(3), 221-241. DOI:[10.1177/0091552114528972](https://doi.org/10.1177/0091552114528972)
- Macan, T. H. (2017). Time management: A process model. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 79(3), 381-391. DOI:[10.1037/0021-9010.79.3.381](https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.79.3.381)
- Pintrich, P. R. (2011). A conceptual framework for assessing motivation and self-regulated learning in college students. *Educational psychology review*, 16(4), 385-407. DOI:[10.1007/s10648-004-0006-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-004-0006-x)